
EFFECT OF FIBER TENSION AND ORIENTATION ON THE PROPERTIES OF GLASS-FIBER/EPOXY FILAMENT WOUND TUBES

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CODE: BCCM7-206

Keywords: Filament winding, fiber tension, winding angle, mechanical properties.

Abstract: Composite tubes, known for their durability and corrosion resistance, play a crucial role in oil extraction and water injection in wells. The production of these tubes is currently carried out by filament winding, a technique that offers a lightweight and robust solution, depositing filaments in layers. Filament tension and winding angle significantly determine the mechanical behavior of the final product, but their precise effect must be evaluated for each application. This work aims to evaluate the effect of filament tension and winding angles on the mechanical properties of composite tubes with glass-fiber/epoxy. Optical microscopy and fiber content analyses were performed on the composite to study fiber content, layer compaction and voids. Tensile testing was conducted according to ASTM D2290-19. The results indicated that applying higher tension resulted in greater compaction and less voids, thereby improving the mechanical performance of the tubes. Also, the change in winding angle affected the level of filament tension, depending on the region and geometry of the manufactured part. Understanding these factors deepens the knowledge about tube manufacturing and provides practical insights for optimizing the filament winding process and to ensure quality and performance of the products including longevity of pipelines, contributing to safety and efficiency.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of high-performance pipes is vital for efficient and reliable transport of crude oil and refined products. Glass-fiber/epoxy tubes present themselves as interesting solutions for pipeline applications due to their superior durability and corrosion resistance. These tubes are manufactured by filament winding (FW), where fiber tension and angle are critical factors, significantly influences the final properties, such as longitudinal strength, circumferential strength, stiffness, and flexibility [1,2].

As the demand for these tubes grows, it becomes imperative to deepen the understanding on how the process parameters affect the mechanical behavior of the composite, being critical for designing robust pipeline systems capable of withstanding varied operating environments, ensuring long-term performance and integrity [3]. The applied winding tension, for instance, significantly affects the fiber content in the composite, which in turn affects its overall performance [4], in a way that, the higher winding tension, the higher the component strength [5,6,7].

This article aims at conducting a detailed investigation into the effects of fiber tension and orientation angle on the mechanical properties of glass-fiber/epoxy tubes, assessing how these two factors interact with each other and how they can be optimized to improve the performance of the tubes.

2. METHODOLOGY

The tubes were produced on a 2-axis filament winding machine, using 1100 Tex glass fiber tows from Owens Corning with 6 threads and a winding band of 36 mm, and epoxy resin from Olin. The Cadfil software was employed to calculate the best trajectories to be followed by the machine. The following lay-ups were used: $[\pm 50]_2$, $[\pm 65]_2$, or $[\pm 80]_2$. The 80° angle maximizes strength in tangential direction, especially when the final product is subjected to internal pressures, whereas the 50° angle may offers a balance of properties in tangential and axial direction [3,4].

The tension applied to the tows in the winding process was adjusted by increasing the path that the tow makes before reaching the metallic mandrel, which results in greater friction with the machine components, as depicted in Figure 1. A wet tow was fastened to a Compac digital dynamometer model IP-500 and pulled, measuring the force needed for the fibers to consistently slide through the components and onto the mandrel. Five measurements were taken for each scenario.

Figure 1. (a) Frictionless fiber, (b) fiber with 50% of maximum friction, (c) fiber with 100% maximum friction.

After winding, the part was cured in an oven. The final part was analyzed by optical microscopy, using a Zeiss brand microscope, Model Axio Lab.A1, with a magnification of 10x. Table 1 presents the nomenclature adopted for the samples. The fiber and resin contents were analyzed using the muffle burning method, according Method I of the ASTM D3171-22, which is based on the weight difference before and after burning of the resin at 600°C , leaving only the fiber. After cooling and weighing of the residue, the fiber and resin contents were calculated. To investigate the mechanical properties, the apparent hoop tensile test was carried out on rings cut from the tubes, based on the ASTM D2290-19 standard. The test was carried out in an universal testing machine Instron 3382 with a 100 kN load cell, as depicted in Figure 2, until the rupture of the specimens. The mean apparent tensile strength was calculated using three test specimens for each type of sample.

Table 1. Nomenclature and conditions analyzed in present study.

Sample	Angle ($^\circ$)	Friction (%)
A50F0		0
A50F50	50	50
A50F100		100
A650F0		0
A65F50	65	50
A65F100		100
A80F0		0
A80F50	80	50
A80F100		100

Figure 2. (a) Dimensions of the test specimen, and (b) Apparatus for the testing according to ASTM D2290-19 standard. [8].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fiber tension measured in the winding process for 0%, 50% and 100% of the maximum friction was 143.2 ± 2.8 N, 186.6 ± 1.34 N and 209.94 ± 1.48 N, respectively. As expected, the force increased with the increase in fiber friction, in turn, exerting greater compaction of the layers of the uncured material onto the mandrel during the winding process.

Higher tension in the fibers causes resin expulsion and greater compaction due to resin expulsion, reducing tube thickness and increasing fiber content [3], as observed in Table 2. Higher tension in the fiber tow reduces its porosity and this may hinder tow impregnation in the resin bath during manufacturing, and this also has the potential to increase fiber content in the final product.

The important effect of fiber tension on compaction, as discussed, and on void content can be better appreciated in Figure 3, which shows greater compaction and reduced voids for the $[\pm 80]_2$ tubes when higher friction is applied.

Table 2. Thickness and content of tubes constituents.

Sample	Thickness (mm)	Fiber weight content (%)
A50F0	2.29	55±5.55
A50F50	2.19	66±1.47
A50F100	1.84	67±6.20
A650F0	1.85	53±2.94
A65F50	1.74	61±3.92
A65F100	1.71	60±1.81
A80F0	1.52	56±5.14
A80F50	1.50	58±4.55
A80F100	1.41	61±5.25

The tensile tests were performed on the samples and the average values, as well as their standard deviation, were calculated and from the experimental results and compiled in Table 3. A higher winding angle results in greater apparent tensile strength, as the load is more distributed to the fibers, resulting in a more linear fracture [4]. This is consistent with the current results, where the tube with a winding angle of 80° showed the highest strength. When the winding angle is less obtuse, such as 50° , resulting in poorer alignment with the load direction and greater stress concentration near the notch.

Comparing A50F0 and A50F100, there was a 35,6% increase in strength, in the same range 24,5% found when comparing A65F0 and A65F100. There was a significant increase of 50.8% when comparing A80F0 and A80F100. This increase is due to the greater compaction of the fibers aligned in the direction of the apparent tensile force. With less resin interspersed between the layers, the fiberglass reinforcements are able to perform more effectively. This is noticeable when examining the mass fraction of fiber and resin, which

increases as the tension applied to the threads during the winding process is increased. However, higher fiber tension results in greater variability in results, indicating process instability. This instability could imply loss in quality in the final product, making it less reliable.

Figure 3. Micrographs of the $[\pm 80]_2$ tubes: (a) A80F0, (b) A80F50, and (c) A80F100. Some of the voids are identified with circles.

Table 3. Maximum load and apparent tensile strength of the tubes.

Conditions	Maximum load (N)	Apparent tensile strength (MPa)
A50F0	6456 ± 17	99.6 ± 0.3
A50F50	6787 ± 37	109.5 ± 0.6
A50F100	8051 ± 214	154.6 ± 4.1
A650F0	7889 ± 14	149.1 ± 0.3
A65F50	8577 ± 4	172.4 ± 0.1
A65F100	9665 ± 320	197.6 ± 6.5
A80F0	6719 ± 58	137.4 ± 1.2
A80F50	8816 ± 32	180.3 ± 0.6
A80F100	13671 ± 902	279.5 ± 18.4

A fractured specimen for each winding angle is presented in Figure 4. The correlation between the fracture and the obtained results can be understood in terms of micro-structure and stress distribution. In the FW process, the winding angle dictates final fiber orientation in the composite part, with a significant impact on material strength [4].

Increasing the force improves efficiency of tubular components in resisting failures, especially under loading in the fiber orientation. Also, an angle close to 90° can maximize tensile strength of the product, as it allows the fibers to be oriented in the direction of the applied load studied in this work, that is, in the hoop direction of tube [5]. However, for process and product standardization, it was observed that higher angles and

higher tensions do not necessarily result in consistently higher-quality tubes. Therefore, the selection of other angles may be reviewed depending on the application.

Figure 4. Fracture of the test specimens: (a) A50F100. (b) A65F100. (c) A80F100.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work investigated the behavior of tubes produced by the wet filament winding process. The increase in force applied during winding resulted in a substantial increase in apparent tensile stress of 35.4% for the samples compared from tubes A50F0 and A50F100, 24.5% for samples A65F0 and A65F100, and 50.8% for A80F0 and A80F100. However, process instability was observed for the highest force. A decrease in size and content of voids was observed, along with an increase in fiber content (5-10%).

The tensile test based on ASTM D2290-19 standard and the microscopic analysis were crucial in confirming the effect of fiber tension on the samples, contributing for a more comprehensive evaluation of the effect of those parameters on mechanical properties of the tubes. This study enabled future research on the field, indicating better approaches to further optimize the design and manufacturing process for tubes used in the oil and gas sector.

4.1. Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

4.2. Acknowledgements

This study was partially funded by Rio Grande dos Sul Foundation (FAPERGS) under grant n° 22/2551-0000839-9 - Inova Clusters Tecnológicos. We also thank Lupatech S/A for their collaboration and support.

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